

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 3.4 Present outputs to the SET Plan Steering Group

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1 INTRODUCTION

This report is an overview of the outputs and recommendations presented by the ZEP/IWG9 secretariat at a variety of significant fora including SET Plan Steering Group events, European Commission initiatives, and other international gatherings such as EC Expert Group meetings, the CCUS Forum, EU Sustainable Energy Week, and the Clean Energy Transition Partnership

1.1 Outputs and recommendations at SET Plan Steering Group events and other EC initiatives

Deliverable 3.4 encompasses the continuous efforts of the Zero Emissions Platform (ZEP) and the Implementation Working Group 9 (IWG9) secretariat to actively engage with key stakeholders by presenting their findings and recommendations. These presentations typically occur at regular intervals throughout the year, aligned with the schedules of the respective events and often take place in Brussels, online, or in a hybrid format.

ZEP has continuously contributed to the European Commission's Carbon Removal Expert Group, conveying ZEP's position on topics such as carbon removal strategies and certification methodologies. There have been four meetings between March 2023 and April 2024, with a fifth meeting planned for October 2024. In addition, ZEP has been involved in several recurring events such as the EU Sustainable Energy Week in 2023 where ZEP hosted a policy session on industrial decarbonisation, highlighting key steps for the successful deployment of CCS/CCU in Europe. During the CCUS Forum 2023 ZEP participated in a panel discussion on the establishment of industrial initiatives on CCS/CCU and how to best involve industry in deployment of industrial carbon management value chains. Furthermore, ZEP moderated a stakeholder session on the role of CCS in the decarbonisation of industry and the current status of CCS in Europe during the 2023 EU Industry Days in Malaga, Spain. The session also emphasised the importance of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure as key enablers for industrial decarbonisation in Europe. Additionally, it addressed the significance of collaboration and knowledge sharing among projects, drawing from the experiences of various CCS/CCU projects.

ZEP's presentation at the 7th ACT Knowledge Sharing Workshop emphasised the importance of CCS and CCU in achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 and highlighted the research and innovation challenges faced in this area. Key points included the significance of partnerships and coordination among stakeholders, the progress and current projects in Europe, and the strategic targets for 2030 under the CCUS SET-Plan. The presentation also discussed the critical need for investment in research and innovation, outlining priorities such as CO₂ capture technologies, transport networks, and storage solutions. The overarching message underscored the essential role of CCS and CCU in the EU's energy transition, the creation of new value chains, and the preservation of jobs in hard-to-abate sectors.

At the 6th H2O20 CCUS & Alternative Fuels Workshop ZEP presented its objectives, such as creating conditions to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 and demonstrating the essential nature of CCS and CCU in reaching this goal. The presentation highlighted the impact of ZEP's policy work, including contributions to the Net Zero Industry Act and industrial carbon management strategy, and discussed the importance of technical reports and the establishment of a future European market for CO₂ transport by ship. The session also covered the CCUS SET-Plan which aims to accelerate the transition through greater coordination among EU, national, industrial, and academic research. Updated CCUS targets for 2030 were presented, concluding with a discussion on the CCUS roadmap to 2030, stressing the urgency to deploy CCS and CCU at scale in the 2020s and outlining actions needed for large-scale development to achieve climate

neutrality. Additionally, a similar presentation was provided at the December 2023 SET Plan Steering Group Meeting.

In early 2024, ZEP's Secretary General attended a Clean Transition Dialogue on Clean Tech hosted by President von der Leyen, as well as a Clean Transition Dialogue on the Steel Industry hosted by Vice-Presidents Vestager and Šefčovič. ZEP's contribution at the Clean Transition Dialogue on Clean tech involved two rounds of discussions with high-level representatives from clean tech industries, financial institutions, and social partners. The dialogue aimed to identify regulatory obstacles, skills, and financing challenges faced by clean tech sectors, highlighting areas needing urgent action and generating ideas to accelerate and scale up investments. The event was closely linked to the Net-Zero Industry Act and focused on enhancing Europe's clean tech industrial base while maintaining competitiveness. The first round emphasised the need for regulatory enabling conditions, such as public funding support, CO2 infrastructure deployment, and a stronger policy framework for low-carbon products. It stressed the urgency for the next Commission to prioritise the regulatory framework on CO2 transport, develop national carbon management strategies, and create a pan-European CO2 transport infrastructure. The second round focused on financing investments, highlighting the need for incentives for emitters to invest in capture projects, a strong EU ETS price, a robust Innovation Fund, and national schemes supporting industrial decarbonisation. The session concluded with the need for the EU to play a significant funding role to derisk projects, unlock long-term investments, and commercialise CCS, ensuring Europe's leadership in the clean tech market.

Most recently, ZEP attended the SET Plan IWG Annual Event which focused on the challenges and needs of the process industry in the context of sustainable development towards 2030 and 2050. The event covered discussions on the Industrial Decarbonisation Plan, emphasising regulatory enabling conditions, financing investments, and the role of technologies like CCS and CCU. The agenda included high-level interactions among industry representatives, policymakers, and financial institutions, aiming to accelerate and scale up investments in clean technology sectors while maintaining competitiveness within the EU market.

These meetings illustrate ZEP's active role in promoting and discussing advancements in carbon management and fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders. The importance of this deliverable lies in its role in fostering collaboration and informing policy decisions. By presenting their outputs and recommendations, the ZEP/IWG9 secretariat ensures that the latest research, insights, and technological advancements in carbon management are communicated to those shaping Europe's energy and climate policies. This not only helps in aligning national and regional efforts with the overarching goals of the EU's climate agenda but also facilitates the sharing of best practices and innovative solutions among member states and stakeholders. Annex A: Overview of events

Annex A includes an overview of the events where the ZEP/IWG9 secretariat presented outputs and recommendations between November 2022 and June 2024.

Meeting	Date	Attendants	Key ZEP contributions
Kick-off meeting of the Carbon Removal Expert Group	7 March 2023	105	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A ZEP representative attended and contributed to the Expert Group meeting, conveying ZEP's position.
Expert group on carbon removals: carbon farming workshop	21-22 June 2023	95	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A ZEP representative attended and contributed to the Expert Group meeting, conveying ZEP's position.
EUSEW 2023: Climate neutral Europe: safeguarding jobs and industrial competitiveness	22 June 2023	140	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hosted a policy session at the EUSEW 2023 Policy Conference on the skills and cost of industrial decarbonisation. Opening presentation: The key steps for successful deployment of CCUS in Europe.
6 th H2020 CCUS & alternative fuels workshop CINEA	20 September 2023	120	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of ZEP/IWG9 and SET Plan targets.
ZEP Stakeholders Session – EU Industry Days 2023	5 October 2023	90	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP moderated a stakeholder session during the EU Industry Days 2023.
7th ACT Knowledge Sharing Workshop	5 October 2023	90	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of ZEP/IWG9 and SET Plan targets.
Expert Group meeting on industrial carbon removal certification methodologies	25-26 October 2023	110	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A ZEP representative attended and contributed to the Expert Group meeting, conveying ZEP's position.
CCUS Forum 2023	28 November 2023	600	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Panellist session: All hands-on deck: establishing industrial initiative on CCS and CCU.
SET Plan Steering Group	14 December 2023	93	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZEP/IWG9 meeting to discuss the CCUS SET Plan 2030 targets; CCUS roadmap; coordination of the implementation plan; and upcoming ZEP actions.
Clean Transition Dialogue on clean tech	22 February 2024	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant in roundtable with President von der Leyen, intervention on importance of CCS/CCU.
Clean Transition Dialogue on steel industry	22 March 2024	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant in roundtable with Vice-Presidents Vestager and

			Sefcovic, intervention on CCS for steel industry.
4th EU Carbon Removals Expert Group meeting	15-17 April 2024	112	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A ZEP representative attended and contributed to the Expert Group meeting, conveying ZEP's position.
SET Plan IWG-Industry 2024 Annual Event - Advancing Sustainable Energy in Industry	5 June 2024	50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A ZEP representative attended the event to discuss the main challenges and needs of the process industry; critical issues to advance the sustainable development of EU's energy-intensive industry towards by 2030 and 2050; and EU-funded projects and SET Plan implementation actions.